

Appendix 1: Search Terms

		PubMed-MEDLINE	SCOPUS	IEEE Xplore	JSTOR	Google Scholar
Intervention	Keywords	("artificial intelligen*" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "decision support" OR "digital technology" OR "Chatbot")	("artificial intelligen*" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "decision support" OR "digital technology" OR "Chatbot")	("artificial intelligen*" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "decision support" OR "digital technology" OR "Chatbot")	("artificial intelligen*" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "decision support" OR "digital technology" OR "Chatbot")	((("Public Health*") AND (artificial intelligence)) AND ("ethic*" OR "Privacy" OR "Autonomy" OR "Principle" OR "Equity" OR "Legal*" OR "security"))
		AND				
Outcome	Keyword	("ethic*" OR "Privacy" OR "Autonomy" OR "Principle" OR "Equity" OR "Legal*" OR "security"))	("ethic*" OR "Privacy" OR "Autonomy" OR "Principle" OR "Equity" OR "Legal*" OR "security"))	("ethic*" OR "Privacy" OR "Autonomy" OR "Principle" OR "Equity" OR "Legal*" OR "security"))	("ethic*" OR "Privacy" OR "Autonomy" OR "Principle" OR "Equity" OR "Legal*" OR "security"))	
		AND				
Population	MeSH	Public Health*	N/A			
	Keywords	Public Health*	Public Health	Public Health*	Public Health*	

Appendix 2: The inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Study undertaken in public health context.
- Study related broadly to the use of Artificial Intelligence.
- Text available in English
- Study that addresses any legal or ethical issues related to the use of artificial intelligence in public health
- Studies that were published from 2015 till 2022
- Peer-reviewed publications, reports, conference proceedings, thesis and dissertations were considered

Exclusion criteria

- Studies focused on clinical settings (imaging, diagnosis, treatment) or focuses on patient level.
- Studies undertaken in non-artificial intelligence context
- Studies that were published before 2015
- Text available in other language rather than English

Appendix 3: PRISMA

Appendix 4: Summary of the included studies:

No.	Authors	Year of publication	Country of Publication	Language	Type of Publication	Journal	Aim of the study	Ethical principles
1	Golbin & et al.	2020	United States	eng	Conference	2020 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)	The data-driven and often black box nature of these systems does not absolve organizations from the social responsibility of increasingly commonplace regulatory requirements to confirm they work as intended and are deployed in a responsible manner, lest they run the risk of reputational damage, regulatory fines, and/or legal action. The legal community should have a good understanding of the responsible development and deployment of artificial intelligence in order to inform, translate, and advise on the legal implications of AI systems.	Bias, fairness, security, safety, privacy, transparency
2	Burr & et al.	2020	London	eng	journal	IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society	By analyzing the ethical challenges of digital psychiatry in different fields, this paper highlights key public health challenges and opportunities, and we offer concrete recommendations regarding how to safeguard and promote the welfare of the public in information societies.	Autonomy, privacy and trust
3	Amann & et al.	2020	Switzerland	eng	Journal	BMC medical informatics and decision making	The purpose of this paper is to assess the role of explainability in medical AI and to make a critical assessment of what explainability means in terms of introducing AI-driven tools into clinical practice.	autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice.
4	Boulos & et al.	2022	Portugal	eng	journal	International journal of health geographics	This article is discussing the issue related to using geospatial data to address public health issues during challenging crises	privacy, confidentiality
5	BÅrre & et al.	2020	Norway	eng	journal Article	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	The aim of this paper is to use the global health sector as a case to show that the EU's guidance leaves too much room for local, contextualized discretion to foster trustworthy AI globally. Global efforts are urgently needed to protect healthcare from the potential harms caused by artificial intelligence technologies	(1) respect for human autonomy (2) prevention of harm (3) fairness (4) explicability
6	Krass & et al.	2021	United States	eng	journal Article	bmj	When a state or federal government seeks to use AI models to predict an individual's risk of covid-19, the key legal questions will ultimately turn on how effective the models are and how much they burden legal interests. We focus on two of the most salient legal concerns under US law: privacy and discrimination.	privacy, discrimination and bias
7	Montgomery & et al,	2018	United States	eng	journal Article	Journal of Information Policy	this article offers key principles and critical issues that must be considered in order to develop effective privacy, equity and consumer protections for the emerging digital health marketplace.	equity, fairness
8	World Health Organization	2021	Switzerland	Eng	Report	WHO Consultation Towards the Development of guidance on ethics and governance of artificial intelligence for health	The participants in the consultation discussed the ethical aspects of the goals and objectives of corporate and non-corporate actors in the health sector.	Privacy and confidentiality, Freedom of choice, control and autonomy, informed consent, Bias
9	Landau, A.Y. and Ferrarello, S. and Blanchard, A. and Cato, K. and Atkins, N. and Salazar, S. and Patton, D.U. and Topaz, M.	2022	United States	Eng	journal Article	Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association : JAMIA	to: (1) identify and describe key issues in development of a machine learning-based risk model and (2) provide a set of recommendations to address these ethical challenges.	equity
10	Gómez-Ramírez, O & et al.	2021	Canada	eng and french	journal Article	Canadian Journal of Public Health	to stimulate purposeful reflection and to provide an orientation to the interrelated, overlapping, and co-constitutive ethical, health equity, and social justice issues that must be considered more broadly in digital public health	health equity, and social justice
11	Bhattacharya & et al.	2021	India	eng	Journal Article	Indian Journal of Community Medicine	to describe the responsible approach to AI design, development, and use from a public health perspective.	Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI
12	Bimczok & et al.	2021	Netherlands	eng	journal Article	South Eastern European Journal of Public Health	to evaluate current legislative gaps in terms of the introduction of AI in healthcare, focusing on the domains of Data Protection, Liability & Transparency, as well as Robustness & Accuracy.	excellence and trust for using artificial intelligence
13	Dankwa-Mullan & et al.	2021	Australia	eng	journal Article	Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved	framework to incorporate ethical AI principles into the development process in ways that intentionally promote racial health equity and social justice	promote racial health equity and social justice
14	Sarbadhikari, S.N. and Pradhan, K.B.	2020	India	eng	journal Article	Safety and Health at Work	enhancing the number and skill sets of the public health professionals, especially the frontline workers, it will be prudent to use the digital health technologies, including artificial intelligence, in enhancing the capacity of the healthcare professional education and delivery	safety
15	Dhingra, D. and Dabas, A.	2020	India	Eng	Global Strategy	Indian Pediatrics	There are four strategic objectives intended to provide guidance and coordination on global digital health transformation and to strengthen synergies between initiatives and stakeholders to improve health outcomes and mitigate associated risks at all levels.	safety, security, privacy, interoperability, and the ethical use of data within and outside the health sector.
16	Thompson, C.L. and Morgan, H.M.	2020	United Kingdom	eng	journal Article	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	This paper discusses the issues highlighted within the code of conduct and the ethical challenges associated with addressing them to successfully integrate artificial intelligence within the NHS.	Transparency, accountability, public trust
17	Luxton, D.D.	2020	United states	Eng	journal Article	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Describe the ethical implications of conversational agents in global public health	bias, privacy, risk of harm, inequitable access
18	Gopichandran & et al.	2020	India	Eng	journal Article	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	describe the ethical challenges of digital health technologies	Safety, protection, Privacy,
19	Boden, L.A. and McKendrick, I.J.	2017	United Kingdom	eng	Journal Article	Frontiers in Public Health	propose a framework to evaluate whether mathematical models that assess human and animal disease risks and control strategies meet standards consistent with ethical "good practice" and are thus "fit for purpose" as evidence in support of policy	principles of biomedical ethics: independence, transparency (autonomy), beneficence/non-maleficence, and justice.
20	Gerke, S & et al.	2020	United States	English	Book Chapter	(Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare)	This chapter will map the ethical and legal challenges posed by AI in healthcare and suggest directions for resolving them.	Informed consent, transparency, safety, fairness, bias, privacy,
21	Blasimme, A. & et al.	2016	Switzerland	eng	Journal	Journal of Public Health Policy	to explore the use and impact of digital technologies for population health and health equity gains.	Equity
22	Bondre, A. & et al.	2021	india	eng	Journal	Global Health: Science and Practice	the authors discuss the challenges in protecting mental health data privacy, guidelines to protect the personal data privacy of individuals with mental health disorders in India, and implications for digital mental health services in other low-resource settings.	Privacy, Confidentiality

Appendix 5: Characteristics of the included studies

Characteristics	Number of studies: 22					
Type of publication	Journal Articles: 19 (16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, 23, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38)		Report: 1 (24)	Conference: 1 (25)	Book Chapter: 1 (38)	
Country	United States: 6	India: 5	UK: 3	Switzerland: 3		
	Portugal: 2	Netherland: 1	South Korea: 1	Canada: 1		
	Australia: 1					
Year of publication	2016: 1	2017: 1	2018:1	2020: 10	2021: 8	2022: 2

Appendix 6: How frequently these principles are mentioned in the literature.

Appendix 7: Ethical challenges related to use of AI in public health

